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Towards Perspective-Based Specification of Machine Learning-Enabled Systems

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Background

Concepts

Machine Learning (ML) is the study of computer algorithms that improve automatically through experience.

- Build a model based on sample data (training data).
- Base its behavior on data.

Requirements Engineering (RE) is the process of defining, documenting and maintaining software requirements. By definition, the requirements for a system are the description of what the system should do.

Merging RE and ML

Context

Machine-learned models are **learned specifications** coming from data.

- Data is the driver of ML.
- Data partly replaces code in a ML system.

The learned behavior of a ML-based system might be incorrect, even if the learning algorithm is implemented correctly.

ML corresponds to the RE phase of a project rather than the implementation phase.

The problem is not that we have implemented the system incorrectly for the given specification, but that we have implemented the wrong specification.

Merging RE and ML

Benefits

ML can benefit from the RE perspective even from studies suggesting that **RE is the most difficult activity** for the development of ML-based systems [1]. For instance:

- RE techniques for ML could help in identifying **quality metrics** beyond accuracy.
- Dealing better with **customer expectations**.
- Understanding why **models do not fit** and for whom they do not fit.
- Which **data is missing** and how the data is analyzed and generalized.

[1] H. Kuwajima, H. Yasuoka, and T. Nakae, "Engineering problems in machine learning systems," *Machine Learning*, vol. 109, no. 5, pp. 1103– 1126, 2020.

How was our proposal born?

A Systematic mapping study

Mapping Study Results

RQ3. What quality characteristics do the RE contributions consider?

Characteristic	Frequency	Characteristic	Frequency
Security	6	Testability	2
Explainability	6	Accountability	2
Privacy	6	Ethics	2
Data quality	5	Accuracy	2
Fairness	5	Suitability	1
Transparency	5	Uncertainty	1
Reliability	4	Autonomy	1
Safety	4	Robustness	1
Performance	3	Modularity	1
Maintainability	3	Scalability	1
Legal requirements	2	Usability	1

How was our proposal born?

An industrial experience

ML-enabled systems needs different **types of teams** to work as expected

- models built by data scientists need to cover quality properties approved by customers and be integrated into other systems/services by software engineers and then be operated and monitored.

A model is just one component of a system as a whole. There are **other components** that require attention:

- Infrastructure
- User experience
- Customer expectations

How was our proposal born?

An industrial oriented publication

Building Intelligent Systems

A Guide to Machine Learning Engineering

—
Geoff Hulten

Our Approach

ML perspective-based task and concern diagram

Our Approach

ML requirements specification template

ML objectives	User Experience Perspective				Infrastructure Perspective	
<u>Problem & context</u>	<u>Accountability</u>	<u>Cost</u>	<u>Forcefulness</u>		<u>Data streaming</u>	
<u>Organizational goals</u>	<u>Frequency</u>	<u>Interactiveness</u>	<u>Value</u>	<u>Visualization</u>		<u>Execution engine</u>
<u>User goals</u>	Data Perspective					<u>Incremental Learning</u>
	<u>Baseline</u>	<u>Data operations</u> E	<u>Distribution</u> E	<u>Quantity</u> E	<u>Source</u>	
<u>Model goals</u>	<u>Timeliness</u>		<u>Inherent data quality</u>		<u>Integration</u>	
<u>ML functionality</u>	Model Perspective					
	<u>Algorithm</u> E	<u>Explainability</u>	<u>Inference time</u>	<u>Input & Output</u> E	<u>Learning time</u>	<u>Storage</u>
<u>Leading indicators</u>	<u>Maintainability</u>	<u>ML problem type</u>	<u>Model performance</u>	<u>Model size</u>	<u>Reproducibility</u>	<u>Telemetry</u>
<u>Customer expectations</u>						

Case Study A

ML requirements specification for Project A

ML objectives	User Experience Perspective				Infrastructure Perspective
Problem & context Strong odors emitted by industrial units that make communities uncomfortable.	Accountability The operator is completely responsible for decisions taken in order to reduce community protests.	Cost The operator shall be aware of the sanctions in case of not preventing community protests.	Forcefulness Taking decisions based on the predictions is not mandatory.		Data streaming The data shall be streamed by the real-time data management system (Microsoft Stream Analytic tool).
Organizational goals Avoid being sanctioned by the environmental authority for emitting strong odors.	Frequency The operator shall receive a prediction every 5 minutes.	Interactiveness The system shall grow data by receiving feedback from user interactions.	Value The operator shall have transparency on the reduction of complains.	Visualization The predictions of the model shall be presented in a dashboard in an interactive way according to the approved prototype.	Execution engine The model shall be deployed in a cloud computing service (Microsoft Azure).
User goals Odor emission alerts shall be accurate and allow decisions to be made to reduce community complains.	Data Perspective				Incremental Learning The data shall be continuously used to retrain the model when needed (data drift detection is required).
	Baseline The data shall meet the constraints (e.g., min max values, data types), defined in the baseline dataset.	Data operations The data shall be normalized, dropped, resampled and encoded as needed.	Distribution The dataset shall be split in some degree into training and test data.	Quantity The training and test dataset shall have data points as needed to build a valuable model.	Source The data shall be searched in a database supported by the third-party data providing service.
Model goals Accuracy, precision, recall shall be higher than 70%	Timeliness The data shall be available for use in real time.		Inherent data quality The data shall be real usage data and meet concerns related to ethics, accuracy, bias, completeness, consistency and credibility as much as possible.		Integration The dashboard shall consume the model as a web service (Microsoft Azure endpoint).
ML functionality Classify the probability (high or low) of emitting strong odors that bother the community.	Model Perspective				Storage The ML artifacts (e.g., model, datasets, experiments) shall be stored in a cloud service on Microsoft Azure.
Leading indicators Daily dashboard usage percentage and reduce the number of complaints from the community in 20%	Algorithm Logistic regression.	Explainability The model shall provide information on the most importance features to explain its decisions.	Inference time The model shall infer its results in less than a minute.	Input & Output Input: refinery variables and meteorological variables. Output: probability of having a community claim.	Learning time Training the model shall take one hour at most.
Customer expectations The system shall accurately classify the probability of emitting strong odors, allowing to prevent community complains.	Maintainability The model creation shall follow best coding practices (e.g., coding conventions PEP-8, SOLID design principals) and be documented according to docstring PEP-257.	ML problem type Predict categories (classification problem).	Model performance The model shall meet accuracy, precision and recall higher than 70%.	Model size The model size shall not break the inference time and the model explainability.	Reproducibility The creation/training of the model shall be automated by using a pipeline.
					Telemetry The system shall collect and allow monitoring user interaction data and model performance.

Case Study B

ML requirements specification for Project B

ML objectives	User Experience Perspective				Infrastructure Perspective	
Problem & context The disproportionate burning of gases causing high money costs.	Accountability The operator is completely responsible for decisions taken in order to reduce the burning gases.	Cost The operator shall be aware of the sanctions in case of not preventing bad burning gases.	Forcefulness Other system shall use the predictions to take automatic actions in the refinery.		Data streaming The videos shall be streamed by accessing the IP address of the camera that points at the flare.	
Organizational goals Increase the refinery's profitability through an efficient safe flare gas burning.	Frequency The operator shall receive a classification of the flare every minute.	Interactiveness The system shall grow data by receiving feedback from user interactions.	Value The operator shall have transparency on the reduction of bad burning gases.	Visualization The predictions of the model shall be presented in a dashboard in an interactive way according to the approved prototype.		Execution engine The model shall be deployed to internal customer servers and consumed locally.
User goals The gas burning classifications shall be accurate allowing the operator to activate the automatic work mode	Data Perspective					Incremental Learning The images shall be continuously used to retrain the model.
	Baseline The images shall meet the constraints (e.g., pixel coordinates, dimensions), defined in the baseline dataset.	Data operations The images shall be extracted from videos, cropped and labeled as needed.	Distribution The images shall be split in some rationale degree into training and test data.	Quantity The training and test dataset shall have images as needed to build a valuable model.	Source The images shall be obtained from videos that are sent by the customer due to permission issues.	
Model goals Accuracy, precision, recall >= 70%	Timeliness The videos from a month ago shall be available for use		Inherent data quality The images shall meet bias, completeness, consistency, credibility and real usage.		Integration The model shall be integrated with an inference engine so that it can define operation operation rules.	
ML functionality Classify through computer vision techniques the gas burning state of the flare.	Model Perspective					
	Algorithm Neural Networks	Explainability Does not apply	Inference time The model shall infer a set of images (40) in less than a minute.	Input \ Output Input: images reflecting all the flare burning states Output: Image classified	Learning time Training the model shall take one day at most.	Storage The ML artifacts shall be stored in a cloud service on Microsoft Azure and recovered in an efficient way.
Leading indicators Percentage of use of the automatic work mode and reduce the money costs of burning gases	Maintainability The model creation shall follow best coding practices (e.g., coding conventions PEP-8, SOLID design principals) and be documented according to docstring PEP-257.	ML problem type Classify images (computer vision technique)	Model performance The model shall be correct at least 70% of the time.	Model size The model size shall not break the inference time.	Reproducibility The creation/training of the model shall be automated by using a pipeline.	Telemetry The system shall collect summary data from user interactions so that it can be monitored.
Customer expectations The system shall accurately classify the flare when burning gases.						

Help us to improve the solution, please

Ease of use, usefulness and feasibility.

<https://forms.gle/c29TytwRN6FV5kWv7>

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Thank you so much for attending

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